

**ANALYSIS AND OPTIMIZATION OF BONDED JOINTS WITH FRP
COMPOSITE TUBES**

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ABSTRACT

Stresses in adhesively bonded tubular lap joints in fibrous composite materials subjected to tensile loading have been analyzed by finite element method using axisymmetric four-noded quadratic isoparametric elements. Variation of different stresses along the adherend-adhesive interface have been graphically displayed. Nomographs for stress concentration factors of the shear and principal stresses with respect to changing joint geometrical parameters like overlap length, adhesive thickness and adhesive end-fillets have been presented. Optimum values of the joint parameters have been established for safe-design and better performance of the tubular joints for different material cases.

Key words: adherend, adhesive, bonded joints, composites, stress-concentration factor.

1. INTRODUCTION

Fabrication of structures or assembly of machine components are made with the help of joints. While transforming load from one member to another, the joints act as locations of high stress concentration and potential failure. Hence, the analysis, optimization and design of joints, and particularly which are made of fibrous composites, generate interest and need special attention, as the FRP materials fully lack the characteristics of ductility to redistribute the locally developed high stresses by yielding as the metals and their alloys generally do. Due to the recent advances in the formation of adhesives, adhesive bonding has emerged as a structurally efficient, simpler and cost-effective fabrication process. Adhesive bonding offers other advantages like the ability to join very thin plates, tubes and bars for which the mechanical fasteners like bolts, rivets, pins etc. are hazardous and totally unfit. Accurate determination of stresses, strains, deflections and locations of their peak values are essential for efficient design of joints. The strength of the joint depends upon the geometrical configurations, mechanical properties, strength and

stiffness of the adherend and the adhesive materials.

Literatures dealing with the stress analysis of adhesively bonded lap joints between flat adherends are abundantly available. But, literature relating to tubular joints with composite materials is very scanty. Lubkin and Reissner [1] have found the theoretical analysis for stresses in tubular lap joints under tensile axial load and have given solution for both the shear stress $\tau_{r\theta}$ and the normal stress σ_r across the thickness of the adhesive layer. They assumed the adhesive layer approximating to an infinite number of shear and tension springs. Their result shows that $\tau_{r\theta}$ and σ_r concentrate at the overlapping ends. The limitations of their analysis are that the joints have only square ends without adhesive spew fillets at the ends of the adhesive interlayer which lacks relevance with practical cases. Further, their analysis is applicable only to isotropic materials. Volkersen [2] has also given a closed form solution for tubular lap joints under axial torque for isotropic cases. Terekhova and Skoryi [3] presented closed form solution for tubular lap joints subjected to external and internal pressures and neglected the effect of adherend bending. Adams and Peppiatt [4] have analyzed the tubular lap joints by finite element method under tension and torsion loading separately. They have also considered tubular scarf joints by finite element method, but with very few elements only. However, the analytical solutions derived by all the investigators referred above, are exclusively applicable to the isotropic materials only. In the present work the authors have tried to find out the peak values of various stresses, their variation in the critical locations of the joint with different FRP composites with a wide variety of joint geometries for obtaining the optimum configuration.

2. FINITE ELEMENT FORMULATION

Figure 1- presents the geometry, loading and boundary conditions of the tubular lap joint. The finite element idealization is shown in -Figure 2-.

The displacement $\{ \bar{u} \}$ within an element is given by

$$\{ \bar{u} \} = [N] \{ a^e \} \quad (1)$$

where $[N]$ is the matrix of shape functions and $\{ a^e \}$ is the vector of nodal displacements. The element stiffness matrix is given by

$$\{ K \} = \int \int \int_V [B]^T [D] [B] dV \quad (2)$$

where $[B]$ is the strain displacement matrix given by

$$\begin{aligned} \{ \epsilon \} &= [B] \{ a^e \} = [L] [N] \{ a^e \} \\ [L] &= \text{Linear operator matrix and} \\ [D] &= \text{Elasticity matrix.} \end{aligned}$$

The elementary volume $dV = r d\theta dr$ and the integration is carried over the entire axisymmetric ring element through $\theta = 0$ to 2π . The assembled equations result into the form

$$\{ r \} = [K] \{ \delta \} \quad (3)$$

Lap length = $2c$; Adhesive thickness = t_g ; Adherend thickness = t_a

(a) Sectional view of tubular lap joint

Adherend $l = 80 \text{ mm}$, $t_a = 1 \text{ mm}$

Adhesive $2c = 10 - 40 \text{ mm}$, $t_g = 0.1 - 0.25 \text{ mm}$, $a = 20 \text{ mm}$

(b) Axisymmetric configuration of tubular lap joint for FRP - Composite

Figure 1. Geometry of tubular lap joint

(a) Complete mesh with boundary conditions

(b) Zoomed mesh at overlap region

(c) Further zoomed mesh at one end of the overlap region

Figure 2. Finite element idealization

where, $\{r\}$ = vector of nodal forces
 $\{\delta\}$ = vector of nodal displacements
and $[K]$ = global stiffness matrix.

The adhesive bonded tubular joints are characterized as axisymmetric and hence, the stress components are independent of the angular θ coordinate and all derivatives with respect to θ vanish. Thus,

$$\gamma_{23} = \gamma_{13} = \tau_{23} = \tau_{13} = 0.$$

The elements of the elasticity matrix $[D]$ for an axisymmetric orthotropic case can be expressed as

$$D_{11} = (E_1 E_2 / m) \{ (E_1 / E_2) - (\nu_{13} + \nu_{12} \nu_{23})^2 E_1 E_3 / (mn) \}$$

$$D_{12} = D_{21} = (E_1 E_2 / m) \{ \nu_{12} - (\nu_{13} + \nu_{12} \nu_{23}) (E_2 \nu_{12} \nu_{13} + E_1 \nu_{23}) E_3 / (mn) \}$$

$$D_{22} = (E_1 E_2 / m) \{ 1 - (\nu_{13} + \nu_{12} \nu_{23}) (E_2 \nu_{12} \nu_{13} + E_1 \nu_{23}) E_3 / (mn) \}$$

$$D_{23} = D_{32} = E_2 E_3 (E_1 \nu_{23} + E_2 \nu_{12} \nu_{13}) / (mn)$$

$$D_{13} = D_{31} = E_1 E_2 E_3 (\nu_{13} + \nu_{12} \nu_{23}) / (mn)$$

$$D_{33} = E_2 E_3 / n$$

$$D_{44} = G_{12} \text{ and } D_{14} = D_{41} = D_{24} = D_{42} = D_{34} = D_{43} = 0$$

where, $m = (E_1 - E_2 \nu_{12}^2)$ and

$$n = \{ E_2 - (\nu_{13}^2 + 2 \nu_{12} \nu_{23} \nu_{13}) E_2 E_3 - \nu_{23}^2 E_1 E_3 \}.$$

The mechanical properties of different composite laminates considered are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Mechanical properties of composite laminates

No.	Material	E_1	E_2	E_3	ν_{12}	ν_{23}	ν_{13}	G_{12}	E_1 / E_2
1	GL/E(UD)	4.85	18.28	18.28	0.25	0.38	0.25	9.14	3.00
2	B/E(UD)	0.98	21.09	21.09	0.30	0.38	0.25	7.03	10.00
3	C/E(UD)	5.00	7.00	7.09	0.34	0.38	0.34	3.50	21.71
4	GR/E(UD)	0.98	5.27	5.27	0.25	0.38	0.25	2.64	40.04
7	Isotropic	0.00	200.00	200.00	0.30	0.30	0.30	8.07	1.00
8	Adhesive	5.00	5.00	5.00	0.35	0.35	0.35	1.90	1.00

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Figures 3(a) and 3(b) show the distribution of normalized peel stress (σ_r) for different overlap lengths and adhesive thicknesses of the joints for GL/E(UD) composite tube. The stress values have been normalized by dividing with the mean applied shear stress, $\tau_m (=F/4\pi ac)$, where a is the radius of the midplane of the adhesive layer. It is observed that highest stress values are located near

(a) Effect of overlap length (b) Effect of adhesive thickness

Figure 3. Effect of overlap length and adhesive thickness on peel stress distribution

(a) Peel stress distribution for different material cases (b) Shear stress distribution for different material cases

Figure 4. Peel and shear stress distributions for different material cases and varying overlap lengths

(a) Variation of SCF with lap length

(c) Variation of SCF with adhesive thickness

(b) Variation of SCF with lap length

(d) Variation of SCF with adhesive thickness

Figure 5. Stress concentration factors for varying joint geometrical parameters and different material cases

the ends of the joints. There exists a steep gradient in stress values at the ends of the adhesive layer and almost zero stress values for a greater portion of the overlap length. The normalized peak stress values increase with increase of overlap length, while the increase of adhesive thickness results in decrease of the peak stress values. Figures 4 (a) and (b) display the distribution of peel, and shear stresses in the joints for different composite materials. Nomographs 5(a) and (b) represent the variations of stress concentration factors of peel and shear stresses respectively with variation of lap lengths, while, -Figures 5(c) and 5(d)- explain the effect of adhesive thickness on the values of SCF of peel and shear stresses in different composite material cases.

4. CONCLUSIONS

- * The highest values of the important stresses concentrate mostly at both ends of the joints spreading over a small portion of the overlap length and in the remaining major interior portion of the lap length the stress values are negligibly small irrespective of adherend materials and geometric configurations.
- * Steep gradients of the stresses exist at the ends of the adhesive inter- layer. This indicates that the failure of the joints by delamination are most likely to incipiate from the joint ends.
- * The peak values of the stresses depend mostly on overlap length, and adhesive thickness.
- * The optimum overlap length is found to be ranging between 20-25 mm. For advanced materials like boron and graphite epoxy composites, the stress concentration factor values are even less than that of isotropic material when overlap length is more than 20 mm.
- * Optimum value of the bonding glue thickness is found to be 0.25 mm for improved performance of the joints.
- * In practice, when a joint is made, excess adhesive flows out to form an adhesive fillet, which can be approximated to a triangular or elliptical shape for the purpose of analysis. This causes considerable reduction in the peak stress values, thereby, enhancing the joint strength.

References

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